

Leveraging 4c Competencies in EFL Classroom

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ABSTRACT

Modifying 4C Competencies in EFL Classrooms Following Pandemic. The adoption of 4C competences in post-pandemic EFL classrooms is the main focus of this study. The researcher employed the descriptive qualitative method. Both observation and interviews were used to get data for this investigation. The lecturer for the class on extensive reading and the second-year English language study program students who were enrolled in it. The Extensive Reading lecturer and students have implemented the 4C skills in the teaching and learning process, according to the data analysis results. Based on the results of the research, the 4C competencies support students' creativity as part of the application of creative competencies. One of the lecturer's assignments in the classroom was to have the students fresh concepts for the content being covered.

INTRODUCTION

There are four abilities that students need to acquire in order to successfully learn English. In this era, we are dealing with the challenges of the twenty-first century, which are considerably different from prior centuries. Science is progressing at an incredible rate in all fields. This century has been very sophisticated, especially in the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) field, it is making this world increasingly narrow (Aeni et al., 2021). Science has advanced greatly in many sectors in this century, particularly in the highly complex field of ICT (Aeni et al., 2021). Because of the sophistication of ICT technology, varied information from various areas of the globe can be accessed instantaneously and rapidly by anybody and from anywhere, and interpersonal communication can be done effortlessly, inexpensively, anytime, and anywhere (Boholano, 2017).

Competitiveness is anticipated to be strong in all spheres of life as a result of the problems of the period of fast globalization, particularly in the more competitive workplace. Enhancing the standard of education at all educational levels is crucial for raising the quality of human resources. It is crucial for the instructor to make the connection between learning and real life and to provide students the skills they need to succeed in life because education serves to address the needs of society (Husain & Kaharu, 2020).

The ability to communicate internationally is one of the difficulties students face as they try to navigate the currents of globalization. Since globalization brings people from many backgrounds together, communication is crucial in the modern world. Since English is a worldwide language and is acknowledged as an international language, it is necessary for individuals from different nations to communicate with one another. In addition, there are more information and educational resources available in English than in other languages, which raises both the importance of learning the language and the role of English in improving educational standards (Diveki, 2022).

Along with communication skills, critical thinking, teamwork, and creativity are essential skills for students in the twenty-first century. Communication and cooperation skills help students build relationships with people in diverse and multicultural workplaces and communities, including those from foreign cultures, in the current global and technology era. Since many of the businesses and vocations with the quickest growth depend on the creative abilities of employees, students who are proficient in critical thinking and creativity are better able to think outside the box, question crowds, imagine novel landscapes, and produce amazing work. Critical thinking and problem-solving abilities enable students to assess information from a variety of sources, including the internet, media, their homes, places of employment, etc.

Students can use these skills to analyze and evaluate information, determine the quality and worth of information, make informed judgments, and take specific actions. These abilities will also help students identify issues, develop answers and alternatives, and explore alternatives if their current strategy fails. These abilities will help students navigate the future real world and serve as a crucial building block for success in college, university, job, and

life beyond the classroom. The main emphasis of these abilities is anticipated to be on preparing students for the future (Erdoğan, 2019).

Some scholars have indicated that 4C competencies enrich the lecturers/educators. In recent years, various studies have been completed in Indonesia that investigated how teachers integrate those skills in classroom instruction. These studies pertain to teachers' competency in implementing 4C competencies. These studies seem to concur that Indonesian teachers still don't have a deep understanding of the 4C abilities or how to use them in the classroom. In one of these investigations, Sari & Wardhani (2020); discovered that some aspiring teachers were still having trouble creating lesson plans that are based on the curriculum, including its 21st-century skill component. Radifan & Dewanti (2020); Barseghyan (2022) also investigated the 4C competencies in EFL Classroom.

These earlier studies constitute one of the factors the researcher takes into account when deciding whether to pursue this line of inquiry. There are similarities and contrasts between earlier studies on 4C skills conducted by various scholars. Most of those studies use a lesson plan as the research's object and the teacher as their subject. The majority of the research's findings demonstrate that the teacher properly implemented the 4C skills in the classroom and in accordance with the lesson plan. Moreover, this study focused on injecting 4C competencies in EFL Classroom after pandemic or post-pandemic situation, which has more challenging atmosphere. The students of course have an online learning habit and it is the main challenging for the researcher to observe it. Regarding to those situations the researchers intended to investigate the adjusting 4C competencies in post pandemic EFL Classroom.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Some scholars have indicated that 4C competencies enrich the lecturers/educators. In recent years, various studies have been completed in Indonesia that investigated how teachers integrate those skills in classroom instruction. These studies pertain to teachers' competency in implementing 4C competencies. These studies seem to concur that Indonesian teachers still don't have a deep understanding of the 4C abilities or how to use them in the classroom. In one of these investigations, Sari & Wardhani (2020); discovered that some aspiring teachers were still having trouble creating lesson plans that are based on the curriculum, including its 21st-century skill component. Radifan & Dewanti (2020); Barseghyan (2022) also investigated the 4C competencies in EFL Classroom.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researcher utilized a qualitative descriptive design. This study got underway on May 12th, 2022. Participants in this study are the students of English language study program in academic year 2020/2021 and lecturers. The researcher describes one lecturer and one class in this article. Two devices were employed in this study's investigation to gather and obtain data. These tools include interviewing and observation. The tool that is used is

observation and interview, which are crucial to obtaining justification and to offering solutions to the research questions specified in the research topic.

“How are the 4C competencies applied in post pandemic EFL classroom?”

The data analysis employed is data analysis in the form of a precise and concrete description of the object that is discussed qualitatively, followed by the presentation of the data in a descriptive manner, i.e., by explaining and describing in accordance with the issues that are closely associated with this research. Data gathering, data condensing, data display, and conclusion drawing/verification are the four steps of the activities that comprise analysis, according to (Miles & Huberman, 2014). The following is the application of 4C competencies in the classroom by lecturer. A from the first meeting of the researcher observed until the last meeting.

Table 1. The Application of Communication Skills in Class A

Lecturer A			
1st Meeting	2nd Meeting	3rd Meeting	4th Meeting
a. The lecturer gives ideas to students when learning in class	a. The lecturer gives ideas to students	a. The lecturer gives ideas to the students	a. The lecturer gives ideas to the students about song
b. There is communication between students and teacher during the learning process in class	b. There is communication between lecturer and students	b. There is communication between lecturer and students	b. Two way communication identify in the learning process
c. The lecturer provides information about conjunction	c. The lecturer provides a review about the hortatory exposition text	c. The lecturer provides information about new materials (song)	c. The lecturer provides information about song
d. The lecturer gives instructions to students in a class	d. The lecturer gives instruction to the students to make a hortatory exposition text in groups	d. The lecturer gives instruction to the students	d. The lecturer always gives instruction to the students in the learning process
		e. The lecturer tell the students about the benefit of learning English through song	e. The lecturer tell the students about the benefit of learning English through song
		f. The lecturer provides	f. The lecturer provides

		contextual learning motivation for students: The lecturer connect the meaning of the song lyric with the daily life	contextual learning motivation for students: The lecturer connect the meaning of the song lyric with the daily life
Students A			
1st Meeting	2nd Meeting	3rd Meeting	4th Meeting
a. The students actively answering the teacher question about conjunction	a. The students actively communicate in the learning process	a. The students actively answering and expressing their opinion about new materials (song)	a. The students give ideas about expressing feeling
b. The students communicate their opinion about the learning materials	b. The students express their ideas in the classroom about hortatory text	b. The students communicate their opinions fluently and confidently	b. The students can communicate their opinion fluently
c. The students make interaction with their classmate	c. The students actively discuss with others in a group work	c. The students make interaction with others	c. The students interact with their classmate in the learning process
	d. The students present their group work in the whiteboard		

According to the table above, there is excellent and frequent communication between teachers and students as well as amongst students themselves. During the teaching and learning process, the teacher frequently engages with the students, always expresses ideas about the subject matter, and delivers instructions to the pupils. The teacher also makes a connection between the knowledge gained that day and daily life, as well as the advantages they receive as a result of the knowledge acquired that day. Students are also

perceived to be actively communicating by using their communication abilities in the classroom, such as asking questions, responding to teacher queries, and confidently and clearly expressing their thoughts.

Table 2. The Application of Collaboration Skills in Class A

Teacher A			
1st Meeting	2nd Meeting	3rd Meeting	4th Meeting
a. The lecturer provide effective explanation about conjunction in hortatory exposition text	a. The lecturer provides explanation about hortatory exposition text	a. The lecturer provides effective explanation about song	a. The lecturer provide effective explanation about the meaning of the song in the textbook
b. The lecturer provides opinion about the assignment	b. The lecturer provides opinion about the theme of the assignment	b. The lecturer give opinion about the song	b. The lecturer share assumption about the meaning of the song
c. The lecturer gives flexibility exercise about conjunction in hortatory exposition text	c. The lecturer devided the students into some group to make a hortatory exposition text	c. The lecturer provides flexibility exercise for the students using some supporting media	c. The lecturer provides flexibility exercise for the students
		d. The lecturer give value and tell the students about the benefit of learning English through song	d. The lecturer collaborate with the students to translate the meaning of the song
			e. The lecturer gives value according to the song that played
Students A			
1st Meeting	2nd Meeting	3rd Meeting	4th Meeting
a. The students sharing information	a. The students actively sharing	a. The students share their opinions about	a. The students share their opinions about

about conjunction in the classroom b. The students collaborate with their friends to finish the assignment	information about their ideas in the learning process b. The students work together in a group to make a hortatory exposition according to the theme given by the teacher	the definition of song b. The students collaborate with others to reach the learning goals	the meaning of the song b. The students collaborate to translate the meaning of the song
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The implementation of cooperation competences in class A has been excellent, as shown by the preceding table. It is evident that educators and learners collaborate to share ideas in order to offer thoughts and insights into the subject matter being taught. One example of a collaborative activity that takes place in the classroom between teachers and students is answering collectively every exercise given by the teacher, interpreting a song, and working in groups to create a text hortatory exposition.

Table 3. The Application of Critical Thinking Skills in Class A

Teacher A			
1st Meeting	2nd Meeting	3rd Meeting	4th Meeting
a. The lecturer ask the students' opinion about conjunction b. The lecturer gives a chance to the students to think and fill the suitable conjunction in the exercise	a. The lecturer gives questions to the students about the function of the part in hortatory exposition text b. The lecturer gives the students some minutes to create their group assignment about hortatory exposition based on their group	a. The lecturer ask the students about the definition of song b. The lecturer give chances to the students to think about the answer of the exercise	a. The lecturer always ask the students' opinion about the exercise in the textbook b. The lecturer give the students' a chance to identify the word missing in the lyric through hear the song c. The lecturer gives the last assignment about song to evaluate their

	theme		understanding
	c. The lecturer gives evaluation to the students as the last assignment in hortatory exposition materials		
Students A			
1 st Meeting	2 nd Meeting	3 rd Meeting	4 th Meeting
a. The students identify the example of conjunction b. The students think their ideas about the suitable conjunction for the assignment	a. The students identify new thing about hortatory exposition text b. The students think propose their ideas about the theme given by the teacher in the classroom	a. The students identify the definition of song before the teacher explain b. The students think their answer about the exercise about song	a. The students identify new word in the song b. The students think and propose their ideas about the missing lyric through hear the song

Based on table 4.3 above, it is clear that instructor A always solicits feedback from the class before explaining a topic. Students have the chance to voice their ideas about the material being studied with Teacher A as well. Additionally, the teacher always asks pupils to evaluate the content they have learned before moving on to the next chapter at the end of each chapter. The teacher's tasks, such as those asking students to guess the lyrics of songs played in class on Song Material, are particularly beneficial in honing their critical thinking skills. Students can also ask questions and share their comments about the newly presented material.

Table 4. The Application of Creativity Skills in Class A

Teacher A			
1 st Meeting	2 nd Meeting	3 rd Meeting	4 th Meeting
a. The lecturer can get the students attention	a. The lecturer creates fun learning condition in	a. The lecturer creates fun learning condition by	a. The lecturer creates fun learning process that

and built fun learning condition and activity	group work	adding some jokes in the learning process	make the students look happy and enthusiasm about the materials of the day
b. The lecturer gives feedback to the students' opinion	b. The lecturer always makes a joke to make the learning atmosphere become fun	b. The lecturer gives feedback to the students opinion about song	b. The lecturer gives feedback to the students opinion about the meaning of the song
c. The lecturer gives conclusion about the learning materials of the day	c. The lecturer gives feedback to the students group work that had been presented in the whiteboard	c. The lecturer makes conclusion at the end of the learning process	c. The lecturer gives conclusion about the materials
	d. The lecturer use handbook and whiteboard in the learning process	d. The lecturer uses speaker, whiteboard, and handbook in the learning process	d. The lecturer uses speaker, whiteboard, and handbook as the learning media

Students A

1st Meeting	2nd Meeting	3rd Meeting	4th Meeting
a. The students create ideas about conjunction	a. The students create a hortatory exposition text in a group	a. The students make ideas about song and the exercise	a. The students create their own ideas about the meaning of the song
	b. The students make conclusion about the materials	b. The students make conclusion about the materials of the day	

In the table of 4.4 above about the use of creativity abilities in the classroom, it can be seen that the teacher is able to create a positive learning environment where students pay close attention and are enthusiastic about the subject matter given by the instructor. Jokes are frequently slipped into lessons by the teachers. Additionally, the teacher always responds in kind to the suggestions or comments made by the pupils and corrects their responses when necessary. Multimedia is used by teachers for teaching. Whiteboards, text books, speakers for musical instruments, and computers are only a few of them. Thus, it can be said that both lecturer and students successfully use creativity skills in the classroom.

Interview Result

Lecturer and students were interviewed about how the 4C competences were used in the classroom. The researcher employed interview protocols to obtain the same data from the lecturer and students. Some of the things the researchers found in the interview will be described as follows:

Interaction in the Classroom

The focus at this point is to know how the interaction happened in the classroom from the students' perspectives. The researcher tries to find out how the interaction occurs in the learning process of English subjects outside of the observation made by the researcher itself. Several answers have been conducted by the researcher regarding the interaction of the teacher and students or the students and students from the students' answers. From the students' answers, the researcher can identify some skills that were applied in the class both by the students and the teacher itself. They are communication and creativity skills.

According to the results of interviews with a number of students, there is interaction between the lecturer and students as well as between students. Some of the students commented on how well the lecturer-student and student-student interactions went. Some of them claimed that the lecturer delivered the materials properly.

Several students spoke about the exchanges that took place while learning English. The interaction, according to them, was firmly formed. As stated by YSR:

"Well, the interaction between the lecturer and the students that took place in the classroom may have been quite good because the teacher explains the materials in the classroom in standard language and easy for the students to understand. In turn, the students are also easier to understand because the teacher explains the materials in front of the class using language that is easily understood by the students." (YSR, Interview, 25 May, 2022)

In addition, NR revealed the interactions that take place in the classroom, saying that:

"According to Sir, I think the interaction is quite good because the learning we do is not monotonous, usually writing but occasionally we are asked to speak, listen, not only write but also improve our English skills by speaking, and every time we are absent we are asked to recite a sentence that will be used as a presence in filling out our attendance." (NR, Interview, 25th May, 2022)

Furthermore SR, a class a student, who is also one of the students, said the following:

"The relationship between professors and students appears to be pretty positive, there seems to be a lot of activity, and there is frequently a dialogue between and students. Then, if there are projects, such group assignments, students and other students can typically actively collaborate with one another, realizing good cooperation in a group effort". (SR, Interview, 25th May 2022)

Delivery of Teachers' Materials

All of the students who were interviewed regarding their experiences in classroom agreed that lecturer always went over the topic in detail before asking questions or assigning homework to the students. According to FR, who said that the teacher prefers to explain the materials first:

"Sir is the type of teacher who wants to give understanding to his students first and then asks his students to be able to be able to rephrase what that has been conveyed or what has been captured from the delivery," the students say. "Sir himself prefers to explain first, so sir wants his students to know the basic concepts of a lesson." (FR, Interview, 25 May, 2022)

In agreement with the previous comment, SR (25 May 2022) expressed a similar viewpoint when he stated that:

"If I look at how Sir delivers the topic over this semester, he prefers to explain first and then ask questions, yet he is dedicated to the textbook so that people can follow it properly."

In Addition, another opinion coming from QAA who said that the teacher tend to explain first, she said that:

"For that, Sis, as far as I know and from what I've seen, sir, explain more, explain first, state the main points and then return them to us as students, so that we may digest them, understand them in relation to these points, and then respond to the questions from sir". (QAA, Interview, 25 May, 2022)

The researcher has eventually come to the conclusion that the lecturer tended to explain the content first before asking the students about it, based on the statements of the students made above. Some students thought it was an excellent approach since it allowed them to comprehend the course material and respond to the teacher's questions.

Learning Atmosphere

The study discovered a description of the instructional setting in the study of English from students' point of view. All of the students who were interviewed made the same point: they believed the lecturer was successful in creating a positive learning environment throughout the teaching and learning process.

One student claimed that the teaching and learning process made him feel relax, stating that:

"Yes, he can because, similar to the material that was delivered, namely the song, sir delivers the subject in a laid-back or not too tense style, with material that is easy to understand. There are always activities that help kids feel relaxed and untense while learning". ((MRH, Interview, 25 May 2022)

Another statements came from AS, who pointed out that the teacher has his own distinctive qualities, such as the gesture and the genuinely entertaining way the teacher delivered the subject. He said:

"I can tell that the learning environment itself is fairly enjoyable from the manner the teacher spoke above. Usually, when someone speaks from above, they can pay more attention and concentrate better. People don't seem bored at all because it's frequently interspersed with jokes, and they aren't overly stiff while studying because of the gestures, which have also come to be recognized". (AS, Interview, 25 May, 2022)

Additionally, QA expressed a similar perspective when she stated that the learning environment is fun. She added that:

"Regarding the learning environment thus far, I am "enjoyable, joyful, because we also as students do not suffer pressure from sir, sir is also categorized as a teacher who understands us because we have never been charged with assignments but are charged with having the abilities, having knowledge." (QA Interview, 25 May, 2022)

The researcher can draw the following conclusions from the statements made by a few students above regarding the learning environment throughout the English class learning process: (1) The instructor can create an effective learning environment. (2) There was no pressure from the lecturer, and the learning environment in the class was joyful, fun, and happy.

Learning Media

Some responses had been gathered in accordance with the students' responses to the question of what media the teacher uses in the classroom and its efficacy. According to the informants, teacher A utilizes many media, including a blackboard, a textbook, an LCD, etc. According to MR, he asserted:

"Whiteboards, LCD projectors, and speakers. It is effective, in my opinion, because if the teacher explains through the media, there are words that we don't understand or know the meaning of, Sir clarifies the meaning of these words so that gradually expanding our vocabulary". (MR, Interview, 25th May, 2022)

FR offers another comparable viewpoint, stating that:

"In order to present the subject itself, we had previously practiced using a whiteboard and speakers, but in recent sessions, sir, you've given us the chance to present using media like LCDs, computers, or pointers that will be utilized in presentations. The media, in my opinion, is incredibly effective since it not only makes studying enjoyable but also modernizes the classroom by making the best use of already available technologies".(FR, Interview 25th May 2022)

Out of the findings of the direct interview that had been conducted, the researcher discovered various media that the teacher frequently used. The lecturer uses both electronic and conventional media, which are both different types of media. Whiteboards and textbooks are considered conventional media, whereas LCD or projector, computer, or laptop are considered electronic media. All of the students who were interviewed agreed that the teacher's use of media in the classroom supports the teaching and learning process well.

Learning Activities

Some students explained some activities based on the findings of the researcher's observations. The researcher discovered that the teaching and learning process had involved several fascinating activities. The creation of movies, reading, listening to music, and other group or individual projects are a few of the activities that have been carried out in the classroom. SR said the following in the direct interview:

"When my friends and I are studying Extensive Reading, we frequently argue the topics covered in the exams or other viral issues since our conclusions about the answers differ. For the project itself, it depends on the material provided. For instance, we were given material about expressing congratulations and asked to create a 5-7 minute drama-related video in groups. At the time, I produced a graduation drama as such I congratulated my colleagues and my other colleagues, who number around seven people". (SR, Interview 25th May 2022)

Along with the aforementioned statements, AA also described several classroom practices for learning English. She stated that:

"Reading some articles and discuss together". (AA, Interview 25th May 2022)

There are several actions that are carried out in the teaching and learning process, it was discovered from the answers given by students during the interview session. The exercises consist of group reading, discussion, a short theater project.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by researchers. The study's subjects, the lecturer and students have done an excellent job of implementing communication competencies. What the researcher found during the observation about how communication skills were applied and integrated in the classroom was in accordance with what the students said in the interview session.

Lesson Plan

All activity plans have been specified in the lesson plan that the instructor has created, based on the lesson plans that the researcher has gathered. There are various parts to a lesson plan, including (a) learning objectives, (b) media/tools, materials, and learning resources, (c) learning steps, and (d) assessment of learning results. In addition, it includes details about the class, like the name of the institution, the subject, the semester, the primary materials, and the hour. The lesson plan that the English teacher has created complies with all government-issued directives. According to government policy, learning objectives, steps (activities) of learning, and assessment of learning (assessment) that must be carried out by teachers are the core components, while the other components are complementary. This is stated in Circular Number 14 of 2019 concerning Simplification of Learning Implementation Plans (RPP).

Communication Competencies

Based on the findings of researches' observations and interviews. The study's subjects, the lecturer and students of Extensive Reading class have done an excellent job of implementing communication competencies. What the students said during the interview session and what the researcher saw during the observation on how communication skills were used and incorporated in the classroom matched. It is commonly known that communication takes place in the classroom between students and teachers as well as between students. It is a constant goal of both professors in classes to foster two-way dialogue. The use of the chalkboard as a written communication medium is one example of the several types of communication that are also carried out by the teacher in the classroom. Additionally, the professor's gestures while illuminating the subject matter are another form of nonverbal communication. Like a student in class who claimed that professors or lecturer's in-class gestures substantially aided him.

This is in line with the United Nations Children's Fund's assertion that communication is a two-way process in which knowledge and understanding are exchanged (UNICEF, 2017). It involves spoken, nonverbal, and written communication in all of its manifestations. According to Selman & Jaedun (2020), great communicators are those who can form expansive and straightforward thoughts, acknowledge each message passed on by various communicators, provide information and ensure the recipient is fully informed, bring out oral and written communication through various media, and be able to select the most suitable media and communication.

Collaboration Competencies

According to the research's findings, lecturer and students have done a great job implementing collaboration competency in the classroom. In order to attain the learning objectives, students and teachers in classes A and B engage in an exchange of ideas throughout class activities to offer thoughts and insights about the subject matter being covered. Fitri & Aeni (2021) defines cooperation as a teaching method whereby teachers and students assist one another in understanding the material being covered.

Lecturer frequently assist students by holding a number of group activities, such as film-making activities, group presentations on hortatory text materials, etc., in addition to what is stated in the lesson plan, where students are divided into several groups to discuss, gather information, re-present, and exchange information. Students will share ideas and collaborate to create a work through this teamwork. According to Scoular, Duckworth, Heard, and Ramalingam's definition from 2020, collaboration is an activity in which two or more learners share knowledge, resources, and expertise from a variety of sources.

Critical Thinking Competencies

According to the research's findings, the lesson plan states that during a critical thinking exercise, students have the chance to identify concepts they have not fully grasped by posing questions about the subject matter. This exercise is in line with what the researchers discovered during observations and

interviews with students where lecturer frequently inquire about the opinions or ideas of the students regarding the subject matter to be studied. This critical thinking exercise undoubtedly aims to improve students' problem-solving skills and their capacity to come up with novel ideas.

According to Atay (2021) students must be able to make sound decisions and judgments based on what they have learned or read, use appropriate inductive and deductive reasoning, research complex systems, and determine how they will interact with one another in order to effectively ']'use critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The lecturer's classroom activities have helped students develop their critical thinking skills by helping them notice new things, work through challenges in groups, and more. etc.

Creativity Competencies

Several activities were conducted in the classroom to foster student creativity as part of the implementation of creative competencies, which was based on the research's findings. The lecturer's task in the classroom included asking students to come up with fresh concepts for the content being covered. According to Barseghyan (2022), creativity is defined as the ability to come up with new, original ideas or products that have real-world applications.

Additionally, to Schiavio et al., (2021) children's creativity can grow properly if it is supported by a number of aspects, such as: 1) Providing adequate mental stimulation. 2) Establishing a favorable environment. 3) The contribution of educators to the growth of creativity. 4) Involvement of the parents. The teacher has already taken the necessary steps to encourage students' original thought. As in creating a favorable learning environment. A conducive, enjoyable, and fascinating learning environment has been created by the lecturer in the classroom according to the research's findings.

This study recommended some implications namely: create and enhance teaching strategies that can boost students' interest in studying English. The lecturer may periodically offer icebreakers that are pertinent to the lesson being taught; these icebreakers might help students who are bored or feeling sleepy during class by, for example, playing games involving punctuation. In order to make learning engaging and to boost students' enthusiasm in learning English, teachers are also expected to be able to make use of current technology advancements as the consummation.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion section contains research findings and The lecturer and students in the classroom of Extensive Reading as the focus of this research, have applied the 4C skills extremely successfully. The detailed activities that the researcher reported in the preceding chapter served as proof. The 4C competences have been included into the classroom activities. It is advised that future scholars who are interested in this subject conduct research on 4C abilities that were not identified in this study. The following researcher can carry out research with the goal of determining what activities can further develop students' 4C abilities in English learning.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research on the topic still needs to be done “Leveraging 4c Competencies in EFL Classroom.”

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